

SMS Related Work Search Returns

Result returned by the Search String for secondary studies that made up the analysis for the related works.

Table 4
Study returned by the search string

Study returned by the search string	Authors	Year
Virtual collaboration competence requirements for entrepreneurship education in sparsely populated areas	Lohikoski, P. and Muhos, M. and Härkönen, J.	2014
Multi-Loop Social Learning for Sustainable Land and Water Governance: Towards a Research Agenda on the Potential of Virtual Learning Platforms	Medema, W. and Wals, A. and Adamowski, J.	2014
Understanding the Influence and Service Type of Trusted Third Party on Consumers' Online Trust: Evidence from Australian B2C Marketplace	Cao, Cong and Yan, Jun and Li, Mengxiang	2016
Adoption of cloud based e-learning: A systematic literature review of adoption factors and theories	Kayali, M.H. and Safie, N. and Mukhtar, M.	2016
Exploring the Role of Social Media in E-Government: An Analysis of Emerging Literature	Dwivedi, Yogesh K. and Rana, Nripendra P. and Tajvidi, Mina and Lal, Banita and Sahu, G. P. and Gupta, Ashish	2017
Big course small talk: twitter and MOOCs — a systematic review of research designs 2011–2017	Costello, E. and Brown, M. and Mhichfil, M.N.G. and Zhang, J.	2018
Charge nurse development: What does the literature say?	Delamater, L. and Hall, N.	2018
Application of blockchain technology in online education	Sun, H. and Wang, X. and Wang, X.	2018
E-Government Usability Evaluation: Insights from A Systematic Literature Review	Lyzara, Ria and Purwandari, Betty and Zulfikar, Muhammad Fadhil and Santoso, Harry Budi and Solichah, Iis	2019
A Society of Gastrointestinal and Endoscopic Surgeons (SAGES) statement on closed social media (Facebook®) groups for clinical education and consultation: issues of informed consent, patient privacy, and surgeon protection	Bittner, J.G., IV and Logghe, H.J. and Kane, E.D. and Goldberg, R.F. and Al-seidi, A. and Aggarwal, R. and Jacob, B.P.	2019
A Survey on Trust Evaluation Based on Machine Learning	Wang, Jingwen and Jing, Xuyang and Yan, Zheng and Fu, Yulong and Pedrycz, Witold and Yang, Laurence T.	2020
Criticism of the role of trust in e-government services	Bayaga, Anass and Kyobe, Michael and Ophoff, Jacques	2020
Security and Privacy Requirements for Electronic Consent: A Systematic Literature Review	Verreydt, Stef and Yskout, Koen and Joosen, Wouter	2021
Learning Path Recommender Systems: A Systematic Mapping	Machado, Guilherme Medeiros and Boyer, Anne	2021

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Study returned by the search string	Authors	Year
Deep learning models to detect online false information: A systematic literature review	Asmaa, R.M.S. and Ali, B.N. and Manar, A.T. and Qassim, N. and Bushra, A.	2021
Predicting Google Classroom Acceptance and Use in STEM Education: Extended UTAUT2 Approach	Mahamud, S. and Fam, S.-F. and Saleh, H. and Kamarudin, M.F. and Wahjono, S.I.	2021
End-user development of virtual simulations for task training: A literature review	Bunæs, T.H. and Karlsen, J.	2021
A Systematic Review on AI-based Proctoring Systems: Past, Present and Future	Nigam, A. and Pasricha, R. and Singh, T. and Churi, P.	2021
Academic dishonesty and trustworthy assessment in online learning: A systematic literature review	Surahman, E. and Wang, T.-H.	2022
Making AI Explainable in the Global South: A Systematic Review	Okolo, Chinasa T. and Dell, Nicola and Vashistha, Aditya	2022
Federated Learning for Healthcare: Systematic Review and Architecture Proposal	Antunes, Rodolfo Stoffel and André da Costa, Cristiano and Küderle, Arne and Yari, Imrana Abdullahi and Eskofier, Björn	2022
A survey on AI and decision support systems in psychiatry – Uncovering a dilemma	Bertl, M. and Ross, P. and Draheim, D.	2022